

COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGNS TO PROMOTE OCEAN LITERACY AND INTEGRATED MULTITROPHIC AQUACULTURE IN TIERRA DEL FUEGO, ARGENTINA

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Many of us are unaware of how our daily actions affect the health of the ocean, its sustainability and many of the resources we depend on. In addition, most of us do not know about the global reach and importance of the sea and oceans in medical, economic, social, political and environmental terms. These aspects could be counterbalanced by providing or improving access to accurate and reliable education about the marine environment. Ocean Literacy's main goal understands the ocean's influence on humans and the influence of humans on the ocean. Lately, many international communities have assigned a large portion of their budgets and efforts to research and innovation programs, in order to reinforce science activity on different topics.

In this context, the All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) arise. ASTRAL is focused on Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) farming, aiming to define, support, and promote sustainable aquaculture production across the Atlantic area. IMTA is the farming of species from different trophic levels in a way that allows one species' uneaten feed and wastes to be used as inputs (fertilizers and feed) for another species. Sharing knowledge and capacity development are among ASTRAL priorities, as well as to build a collaborative ecosystem along the Atlantic Ocean with industrial partners, scientists, policymakers, social representatives, and other relevant stakeholders.

ASTRAL is committed to increasing the public acceptance and awareness of aquaculture by fostering public understanding of the value of aquaculture and especially IMTA, as a sustainable way to produce aquatic products. In Tierra del Fuego (Argentina), southernmost South America, we had to face the distrust of the local community on aquaculture as a production alternative due to a previous "no to salmon farming" campaign which was very popular. Therefore, several interviews in local radio and TV programs (at a local and national scale) were held in order to communicate and introduce society to other aquaculture systems. The project works with a multilayer stakeholder approach; therefore, we design different Ocean Literacy activities to be held in Tierra del Fuego, mainly in Ushuaia city and a nearby, small fishing village, Puerto Almanza to ensure that the message reaches all the sectors of interest. Some of the activities performed were oriented mainly to primary and secondary schools receiving kids and teachers at the research institution (CADIC-CONICET), organizing and participating in science fairs, giving lectures where we told stories, and we presented native species (that could be used in IMTA systems locally) through pictures and video images (Figure 1). Other activities include an apprenticeship program for early university students at CADIC-CONICET, workshops with local authorities, and training courses with technicians of the fisheries secretary, among others. It is worth mentioning an international course on the actual state of the art of aquaculture in Argentina that was held in Ushuaia on May 2023.

Up to the day, ASTRAL continues to interact with the local community by contributing to an educational project called "A window to the sea" (*Una Ventana al mar*), orientated to teachers for first educational levels, whose main goal is to teach Ocean Literacy, introduce

native species and has a special chapter on sustainable and regenerative practices such as IMTA (Figure 2).

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Figure 1. A) Science fair at CADIC-CONICET, B) Lecture at Puerto Almanza School, C) Workshop multitrophic aquaculture and society.

Figure 2. “A window to the sea” (*Una ventana al mar*) educational program’ didactical material (top) and educators’ capacity building program (down).